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Cross Disciplinary Capstone projects for undergraduate engineering double degree students – the good, the bad and the ugly

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ABSTRACT

In the context of engineering education, “Final Year Projects (Research)”, also known as “Capstone Projects”, are used to demonstrate students’ final achievement based on the skills, knowledge, and experience gained through the whole engineering degree program. In another words, these subjects are designed to bring together all aspects of students’ experiences. Also, it is believed that students should demonstrate professional skills such as: team work, and communication skills as well as knowledge in the field of engineering. For double degree students studying both Engineering and Business at Swinburne University, Australia the final year projects require students to combine and demonstrate their expertise and skills in both disciplines – Engineering and Business. This paper investigates the pedagogy in the final year research project subjects for double degree students. The researchers are investigating the practises relating to the supervision of these multidisciplinary capstone projects in order to improve the learning and teaching experience for students and academics,. Interviews have been conducted with supervisors from both disciplines. Preliminary findings indicate that most supervisors would be happy to work more collaboratively to develop a clearer understanding of the problem under investigation, using cross disciplinary perspectives, with a key focus on critical points during the semester. A superior solution to the problem being investigated can only be achieved through working collaboratively together.

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1 INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Most academic staff in engineering and technology programs believe that the final project for engineering students (known as Capstone) should be used to demonstrate professional skills in addition to practise in the field of knowledge of the engineering discipline. Non-governmental organisations, such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET), encourage students to gain experience in team work, communication and technical engineering design processes through their degree programs including in final year projects (ABET, 2009).

Employers are chasing 'T-shaped' rather than 'I-shaped' graduates. 'I-shaped' professionals predominantly have highly specialised knowledge whereas 'T-shaped' professional are able to blend 'deep knowledge in a field with inter-disciplinary intelligence, reinforced with a strong set of people or soft skills, which facilitate the spanning of boundaries (collaboration) within and outside the organization' (The Collegiate Employment Research Institute, 2012). Final year projects in Engineering, where students demonstrate their professional skills in addition to applying their engineering knowledge, have been part of the curriculum for many years. They facilitate the development of core soft skills such as oral and written communications, team work and time management (as expected by ABET) as well as technical engineering design processes helping graduates become 'T-shaped' professionals. Such projects have been traditionally focussed on a single field of knowledge and have been used to demonstrate students' final achievement based on the skills, knowledge, and experience gained through the whole engineering degree program (Ward, 2013). The ultimate goal is to develop graduates with professional engineering skills such as data interpretation, application of theory, problem solving, and design, along with soft or employability skills.

For double degree students studying both Engineering and Business at Swinburne University of Technology, Australia, the final projects are designed to help students combine and demonstrate their expertise and skills in two disciplines – Engineering and Business. Final year students may be completing Engineering specialisations such as Mechanical, Civil, Robotics & Mechatronics, and Electrical and Electronics. There is also a broad range of Business specialisations covered including Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Finance, and Management. Students undertake a yearlong research project with two supervisors, one from Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology (FSET) and one from the Faculty of Business and Law (FBL). A few of these projects have been done in collaboration with industry partners.

Capstones by their nature are multifaceted and complex. Lee and Lorton (2015) define capstones as 'substantial culminating learning experiences that take place in the final stage of an educational course, offering closure and a focus for the sense of achievement that comes with completion' (p. 1). Capstones require careful design and skilful teaching to maximise the outcomes for all stakeholders. There is a growing body of literature on Capstone units much of which is focussed on the objectives (Rasul, et al., 2016), forms (Ku & Goh, 2010), and curriculum design (Lloyd, 2016; Ward, 2013). To date little attention has been focussed on the pedagogy and how to prepare and develop academics to teach into integrated cross-disciplinary Capstone subjects.

This paper investigates the pedagogy in the final year research project subjects for double degree students. The researchers who co-convene the subjects, one from Engineering and one from Business, have identified issues and problems relating to the students' learning experience throughout the year long project. These issues can be summarised as lack of acknowledgement by some engineering supervisors that students are undertaking a joint rather than a single degree and hence the project

needs to cover both engineering and business domains; lack of clarity as to how project topics are determined; and lack of communication and collaboration between supervisors from the two faculties resulting in differing expectations.

This study investigates these issues in order to provide guidelines for the effective running of multidisciplinary capstone projects at undergraduate level, to optimise the learning and teaching experience for students and academics.

2 METHODOLOGY

Since 2015, Swinburne University of Technology has been offering joint Capstone projects to final year double degree students completing both Engineering and Business degrees. A joint Capstone experience has been developed which inextricably link both disciplines whereby about 100 students per year complete research projects, generally in teams of up to 4 students. Ethics approval was granted to conduct interviews with experienced supervisors from both disciplines, to explore the following issues:

1. To assess whether engineering and business supervisors understand the rationale for offering joint Capstone subjects
2. To determine the level of cross faculty interaction in relation to the supervision of the projects
3. To identify how research project topics are determined.

In total 21 supervisors were interviewed including 13 academic supervisors from Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology (FSET) and 8 academic supervisors from Faculty of Business and Law (FBL). Interviews were recorded and transcribed and themes were categorised.

3 FINDINGS FROM INTERVIEWS

3.1 Engineering supervisors

Thirteen interviews were conducted with engineering academics who had experience in the Capstone supervision role. All participants had supervised both single and double degree project teams. The first issue explored related to the reasons for offering joint Capstone project subjects. A wide range of responses were received. Some academics did not provide any comments and just focused on their role as engineering supervisors, saying for example *'I am only expert in my field'* and had no comments about other fields; others mentioned that it is a good approach, *'but it depended on the topic itself, some topics were suitable for both engineering and business related and some are pure engineering themes'*. One or two supervisors mentioned that offering joint Capstones was part of the university's policy.

The second issue explored related to communication between the engineering and business supervisors. Most of participants said that they had very few joint meetings with their counterparts. Some noted that they met them only during the presentations which are conducted at the end of each semester. Respondents often mentioned that students had separate meetings with their two supervisors. This may have been caused by the fact that the students themselves had organised for different meetings times with each supervisor. Also, it was clear from engineering supervisors that they mainly had communication with the subject convenor from FSET (one of authors of this paper) and had not approached the business coordinator of these subjects. Sometimes, their questions did not relate to the business part of the project so they believed they should not contact the business academic directly.

The third issue explored related to the way in which research topics are determined. Participants were asked if they prefer to identify a topic themselves, allow students to suggest a topic, or seek an industry partner and work on topic development with them. Again, a variety of responses were received with some supervisors welcoming all options, whilst some others preferred only to supervise projects on topics relating to their expertise and nominated by themselves. They stated different pros and cons for each options and then said that it depended upon personal interests and the nature of the topics. For example, industry projects are authentic and help students prepare for the real world, but some supervisors feel that they may be out of their comfort zone or area of expertise to supervise these projects. For student initiated topics some academics felt that whilst students were highly motivated to complete a project they had self-selected, students lacked the expertise to properly define the scope and could end up with either a superficial outcome or unrealistic expectations of what could be achieved in the given time frame by a student team. One of the disadvantages of engineering academics nominating the topic related to the fact that some academics are working in theoretical or technical areas where there is a lack of synergy with a business area.

When asked if they would be prepared to supervise projects on topics nominated by business supervisors, there were virtually no positive responses to this suggestion as the engineering supervisors could not see how this option might work.

Capstone projects have been offered by FSET for a couple of decades for single degree students. Therefore most of the engineering supervisors were familiar with the way these units were delivered, supervised and assessed. From the interviews as well as feedback from the students, it seems that the engineering academics' approach to the final year or Capstone projects is based on their previous experiences in the single degree and they are not prepared or interested to change their mind-set and approach for double degree students. This may be due to self-preservation as many of the academics interviewed concurrently supervise single and double degree students sometimes with similar research topics, therefore, switching from one mind-set to another one may not be an easy task for them. It seems that the respondents prioritise the engineering themes over the business themes of projects for double degree students, as these students are likely to be primarily employed as graduate engineers and draw on their knowledge of business later.

3.2 Business supervisors

Eight interviews were conducted with business supervisors who had experience in the supervision of the double degree projects. There are fewer Business supervisors involved in the FYRP than engineering supervisors as many Business academics supervise multiple teams each year. Many of these academics had also supervised Business Capstone projects, which are all based on finding solutions to authentic problems from industry clients. When the business academics were asked why they think the joint Capstone projects were offered, the majority of responses identified the benefits of offering multidisciplinary projects. They thought it is a good approach to require students to consider the business components of the engineering projects. The wording they used varied, but the general feelings were positive. One supervisor said: *'So I reckon, from my perspective it's so important, and I think every technical field, like engineering and medicine and all that sort of stuff, needs some form of understanding of business...'*. Another participant said *'It's really beneficial for them to actually know things such as commercialisation, or investments, or basically how to get products from a concept stage into a commercialised product'*.

In response to the question relating to collaborations between themselves and supervisors from FSET most of respondents reported that they had not developed a strong relationship with the engineering supervisors. Some had managed to have one or two meetings during the semester. In one case, there were no meetings at all, whilst in another case there were many joint meetings. Several respondents mentioned the difficulties of finding a mutually convenient time that suited both the academic supervisors as well as the students who worked on the project, as many students have commitments including studies and part or full time work.

With regards to communication with both subject convenors (subject coordinators), the business supervisors stated that there were no problem with communication during semester and they were equally happy approaching and liaising with either or both subject convenors.

Interestingly, in regards to the question relating to the nomination of the research topics, almost all business supervisors pointed out that they did not want to initiate the research topics. One said: *“That would be scary”*. Almost all respondents said that starting off a project with a business theme without an engineering theme would be extremely complex, especially if it is not known if there will be an available engineering supervisor with the expertise to support and supervise the project. Business academics were also uncertain they could readily nominate a research topic that would be of interest to the double degree students.

On the other hand, almost all business supervisors mentioned that they would like to have conversation with engineering supervisors before the commencement of semester so they could co-develop the topic, or work together to find a suitable business topic that dovetails with the engineering topic. They thought it would be helpful for them to understand the engineering topic first, and then they would be in a better position to propose the business theme that students could focus on.

Finally, when asked whether it might be a good idea to approach research centres to help with the identification of multidisciplinary projects the majority of respondents did not support this idea. They felt that it was likely to cause more difficulties and challenges for academic staff as well as students, and they did not feel the research centres would be prepared to engage with undergraduate students. Research centres have clear performance indicators relating to income and publications and working with undergraduate students on final year projects falls outside their scope. A summary of the key findings is presented in Table 1 below.

Issue	Engineering	Business
Understanding the rationale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seems like a good approach • University requirement • Unsure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identified the benefits of multidisciplinary projects
Cross faculty interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Few joint meetings • Only through formal presentations • Communications via the convenors but not between supervisors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some had developed relationships and held joint meetings • Difficult to coordinate and find mutually convenient times
Initiation of project topic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some were open to a variety of methods • Others preferred to focus on their areas of expertise • Identified pros and cons but insistent that topics needed to be engineering led 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Had no interest in initiating the topic • Happy to co-develop topics with engineering • Felt that research centres had no interest in UG projects

Table 1: Summary of findings by discipline area

4 DISCUSSION

After interviewing academics the researchers tried to locate models to assist to bring the academics from both disciplines together. Multidisciplinary teaching is not uncommon in areas relating to health related disciplines but little has been published in relation to such practices in other disciplinary combinations. The literature on team teaching, defined as “All arrangements that include two or more faculty in some level of collaboration in the planning and delivery of a course” (Davis, 1995, p.8) provides some practical guidance and notes that there are four areas where pedagogical variations can occur namely in planning, content integration, teaching and evaluation. Shibly (2006) emphasises the importance of careful planning when teaching in interdisciplinary teams, and notes however that this does not guarantee that the intended outcomes will be achieved.

A chapter in the book *Engineering Practice in a Global Context, Understanding the Technical and the Social* edited by Williams, Figueiredo and Trevelyan (2013) was identified where Adams and Forin (2013) present a model to address cross-disciplinary practices. Adams and Forin (2013) undertook a study ‘to investigate critical differences in the ways people experience and make sense of cross-disciplinary practice in engineering contexts’ (p. 105). From interviews with professionals including some in educational and/or research contexts; they developed the framework presented in Figure 1 which provides a useful framework for capacity building within the teaching team.

There is a need to move beyond the traditional constraints of the disciplinary boundaries and mind-sets which involves communication and collaboration. This is more challenging than it may appear as some really bright people find it difficult to work in new ways (Adams and Forin, 2013). Relationally, the progression from Category 1 to Category 4 represents increasingly complex ways of experiencing cross-disciplinary practice and a growing awareness and comprehension of cross-disciplinary practice.

The first and lowest level category illustrates cross-disciplinary practice as working together with people who have different training to effectively find a better solution. Critical attributes of the experiences associated with this category include: (1) knowing what you and others contribute and points of synergy, (2) recognising disciplinary differences in what people do and how they communicate; an iterative process of asking questions, challenging assumptions, and listening for understanding, (3) being comfortable with asking for information that might seem obvious to an expert in that domain, and (4) taking personal responsibility to be an effective collaborator (Adams and Forin, 2013, p. 109).

Fig. 1. Hierarchical model depicting ways of experiencing cross-disciplinary practice (Source: Adams and Forin, 2013 p.109)

Whilst the 4 categories are hierarchical and aspirational, at this stage, the main focus for the researchers in this study is to develop a plan to implement the first level, that is to unify the teaching team so they are able to work collaboratively, using a consistent approach. If this can be achieved, there will be ultimately superior outcomes for all stakeholders. This, in turn, may organically lead to the second stage, which is Intentional Learning. It also found that the third stage of the model, Strategic Leadership, which is very important in the current case of interdisciplinary Capstone projects, already exists as the introduction of the Capstones and the development of the FYRP has been supported by senior management at Swinburne for many years. They are fully supportive of increasing collaboration between supervisors.

Findings from the interviews of both engineering and business supervisors confirm that although in some instances there was some interaction and co-supervision generally there was a lack of communication and collaboration between the counterparts. Overall, they had no or very few joint meetings. Aligned with Adams and Forin (2013) the first step to facilitate effective cross-disciplinary supervision is to get the supervisory panel to meet and work together throughout the FYRP journey in a meaningful way and thereby develop an understanding and appreciation of the problems under investigated from a multidisciplinary stance.

Implementing this requires a strong and well-designed plan therefore a series of forums have been planned at strategically important times throughout the academic calendar. The first forum occurred well before the commencement of the semester, with four principles aims. Firstly so staff from the two faculties could meet one another; secondly to assist with the identification of suitable topics ensuring that both Engineering and Business disciplines were equally incorporated; thirdly to encourage ongoing collaboration and co-supervision; and finally to provide academics with an opportunity to ask any questions or seek clarification on expectations. The next forum was held about one month into the semester, once all project teams had been formed and supervisors had been allocated, as well as research topics finalised. The focus of this forum was to explain all the assessment tasks and marking rubrics, and again answer any questions from the supervisors. The third forum will be held about two thirds of the way through the semester during which time the assessment tasks will again be explained, as well as the marking process, but the main focus of this forum will be to give staff an opportunity to discuss any issues that they or their teams may be facing.

In the second semester the plan is to reduce the number of forums to allow academics to focus on co-supervising their student teams. One forum will be held during the first month of semester, as a welcome back meeting, to maintain the momentum and traction from the forums in the first semester, and also to explain the expectations and assessment tasks for the final semester. The researchers are contemplating using a discussion board on the learning management system about two thirds of the way through the semester, which will focus on any hot topics, issues or concerns that the supervisors may be facing. The discussion will be moderated by the co-convenors and offer staff the opportunity to virtually share their experiences with one another. Through these forums both physical and virtual it is hoped that the first stage of Adams and Forin's model will have been achieved, and all supervisors will develop consistent approaches, perceptions and mind-set.

With relation to the identification of suitable research topics the interviews revealed that it is preferable for project topics to be nominated first by engineering supervisors, and then, through conversations with the business supervisors, design or define the business theme for the particular project. Whilst industry led authentic projects are preferred these can be difficult to source, negotiate and supervise. It seems unlikely

that research centres would be interested in working with FYRP students, for a variety of reasons, so this option will not be pursued.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Joint capstone projects such as the ones offered at Swinburne University to students studying double degrees combining Engineering with Business provide graduates with a unique opportunity to draw upon and integrate their learnings and apply these to a complex cross-disciplinary project which sets them up with the skills expected by industry. An innovation as complex and important as this needs careful management and design to ensure that the intended outcomes are achieved, and stakeholders have a sense of achievement and pride in the experience and outcomes. This does not happen on its own; it must be coordinated as some academics are used to only working within their own discipline areas.

Whilst to date the co-convenors have tried to accommodate students' requests as well as supervisors idiosyncrasies this has led to mixed messages, inconsistent expectations as well as poor experiences for some. Therefore a more strategic and carefully orchestrated approach is being trialled, with a lot more effort and energy invested into the management, coordination and formalised opportunities for collaboration and communication between supervisors (as described in section 4 above), in order to maximise the outcomes for all stakeholders. This should result in improved learning as well as superior experience for students and academics. In addition, it will provide a role model for the graduates as they transition to the workplace, highlighting the power of working collaboratively across discipline boundaries.

Preliminary findings indicate that most supervisors say they would be happy to work more collaboratively to develop a clearer understanding of the problem under investigation, using cross-disciplinary perspectives, with a key focus on three critical points during the first semester, and two critical points in the second semester. Having said that, this requires leadership and direction. The ultimate aim is to create a pedagogical framework to guide supervisors, so that holistic outcomes can be achieved which respect and appreciate the cross-disciplinary nature of the problems under investigation. This should hopefully offer students an optimal experience in their final year of study, as they graduate and become young professionals working in complex and evolving contexts.

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